

1 **Beta genus HPV cell culture model.**

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7 Alpha genus HPVs infect the anogenital mucosa of the genital and oral tissues while beta genus HPVs
8 infect the skin. We established transcriptomic means for study of a beta genus HPV cell culture model. We
9 used a quantitative method for isolation of similarities and differences between E7 protein of known
10 high-risk types HPV16 and HPV18, and of the E7 protein of beta genus HPV38b to study papillomavirus
11 type differences at the molecular level. Type 16 and type 18 E7 protein activated expression of the
12 intermediate filament Ina and Nefh. Similarly, only type 16 and type 18 alpha genus E7 protein *Lrrc10b*
13 and silenced Wnt16. In contrast, only expression of E7 protein of beta genus type 38b resulted in
14 activation of *Pard6g*, demonstrating control of polarity and junctional biology by the E7 oncoprotein of a
15 beta genus papillomavirus.

16 Citations

17 1. Yutsudo, M., Kanda, R., Tanigaki, T., Kitano, Y. and Hakura, A., 1986. Human papillomavirus type
18 38 isolated from patients with epidermodysplasia verruciformis. *Intervirology*, 26(1-2), pp.104-108.

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